

Role of Multidetector Computed Tomography with CT Angiography as the First Line Imaging in Diagnosis of Acute Mesenteric Ischaemia - A North India Centre Experience

Rashmi Rekha¹, Aparajita Mishra², Prashant Sinha³, Roopak Dubey⁴, Aakriti Hans⁵, Sreedhar Mohan Menon⁶

¹Associate Professor, Department of Radio-diagnosis, Sri Ram Murti Smarak Institute of Medical Sciences, Bareilly, UP, India.

²Senior Resident, Department of Community Medicine, Rohilkhand Medical College, Bareilly, UP, India.

³Assistant Professor, Department of Radio-diagnosis, Varun Arjun Medical College, Shahjahanpur, UP, India.

⁴Senior Resident, Department of Radio-diagnosis, Varun Arjun Medical College, Shahjahanpur, UP, India.

⁵PG Resident, Department of Radio-diagnosis, Varun Arjun Medical College, Shahjahanpur, UP, India.

⁶PG Resident, Department of Radio-diagnosis, Kalinga Institute of Medical Sciences, Bhubaneswar, Odisha, India.

Received: 24-07-2022 / Revised: 23-08-2022 / Accepted: 11-09-2022

Corresponding author: Dr Roopak Dubey

Conflict of interest: Nil

Abstract

Introduction: Acute mesenteric ischemia is a vascular emergency with critically important first few hours after the onset of symptoms for successful treatment. CT angiography with Biphasic contrast enhanced multidetector computed tomography is the first-line imaging test for its early diagnosis, detecting underlying causes and for excluding other causes of acute abdomen. CT angiography being non-invasive vascular imaging modality, help to localize the exact site and degree of occlusion that help to determine the choice of treatment. The main aims of this paper was to assess the role of Computed Tomography Angiography along with Multidetector Computed Tomography in the diagnosis of acute mesenteric ischemia and to recognize the characteristic MDCT findings of acute mesenteric ischemia.

Materials and methods: This prospective study was conducted in a tertiary referral centre and teaching hospital from North India (Uttar Pradesh) over a period of ~5 years from July 2017 to August 2022. 140 patients with high index clinical suspicion of having acute mesenteric vascular ischemia were examined with Multi Detector Computed Tomography and Computed Tomography Angiography. They were evaluated for abnormal mesenteric vascular changes and characteristic bowel wall changes.

Results: MDCT combined with CTA showed abnormal findings in 30 patients diagnostic of mesenteric vascular ischaemia. MDCT findings alone were nonspecific for detection of acute mesenteric ischemia.

Conclusion: The sensitivity & specificity of CTA along with MDCT in the diagnosis of AMI after surgical confirmation were 100% and 90% respectively.

Keywords: Acute mesenteric ischaemia (AMI), Multidetector CT (MDCT), CT Angiography (CTA)

This is an Open Access article that uses a funding model which does not charge readers or their institutions for access and distributed under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution License (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0>) and the Budapest Open Access

Introduction

Acute mesenteric ischemia (AMI) is a rare life-threatening condition associated with catastrophic abdominal events and its diagnosis has always remained an interdisciplinary challenge in clinical medicine. With prompt management the mortality rate is seen between 0% to 10%, increases to 50%–60% with a treatment delay of 6–12 hours, further increasing to 80%–100% with a delay of more than 24 hours after the onset of clinical symptoms [1].

Therefore, early diagnosis and prompt management are mandatory in patients with acute mesenteric ischemia. It may be either occlusive or non-occlusive with the primary etiology further divided into arterial and venous occlusion with superior mesenteric arterial embolism (MAE, 50%), mesenteric arterial thrombosis (MAT, 15-25%), superior mesenteric venous thrombosis (MVT, 5-15%) or non-occlusive mesenteric ischemia (NOMI) [2,3].

The arterial causes of AMI are far more common than venous causes. The mortality rates between arterial AMI and venous AMI and between NOMI and venous AMI show statistically significant differences [4]. Because of nonspecific clinical presentation and laboratory test results, imaging studies play an important role in the diagnosis of acute mesenteric ischemia. Multidetector CT should be the first-line imaging modality in strong clinical suspicion of AMI and is the most sensitive and specific diagnostic tool.

CT Angiography (CTA) has essentially replaced catheter angiography as the diagnostic tool of choice for mesenteric ischemia. Catheter angiography is now reserved for stable patients with suspected NOMI and for endovascular management of AMI [5]. So, aim of this study was to assess the role of MDCT along with CTA in the diagnosis of acute mesenteric

ischemia and to recognize its characteristic imaging findings.

Materials and Methods

This prospective study was performed between July 2017 to August 2022 over a period of ~ 5 years in a tertiary care referral centre and teaching hospital from North India on 140 consecutive patients referred from the emergency department and the outpatient clinics of general surgery department with high degree clinical suspicion of having mesenteric vascular ischaemia. Approval for the study was taken from the institutional ethics review committee, informed and written consent was acquired from all the participants. 30 patients comprised the final study group in which 22 were confirmed surgically.

The criteria for patient selection were

1. Sudden onset severe abdominal pain out of proportion to clinical findings.
2. Elevated serum l-lactate and D dimer levels.

The criteria for patient exclusion were

1. Prior history of severe allergic reaction to IV contrast.
2. Contraindications to intravenous contrast material.
3. Known pre-existing renal insufficiency.

All patients were examined with 128 slice multidetector CT system, firstly with non-contrast enhanced CT images. We performed CTA using a biphasic mesenteric protocol with both arterial and venous phase imaging using the scan delay technique; images were obtained 30s and 55-65s after initiation of intravenous contrast injection respectively.

Negative oral contrast (water) or no oral contrast was used to allow visualization of the bowel (water 1000-1200 ml as per patient's tolerance) over 1-2 hrs before

performing CT. We used 125-150 ml of Nonionic contrast medium (Iopromide 300mgI/ml) in a dose of 1.5 ml/kg body weight through 18- gauge intravenous cannula in antecubital vein at a rate 3-4 ml/s with the help of automatic injector. Images was obtained from the xiphoid process to symphysis pubis with Slice thickness = 1.5 mm, kV =120, mAs = 350, 0.4s gantry rotation and detector pitch 1.0-2.0. We used Bolus tracking method to optimize the acquisition phase with the enhancement threshold set at 150 HU. All data sets were then reconstructed as 0.5 mm section thickness at 0.5 mm intervals and transferred to a workstation as multiplanar reformatted images (MPR), curved planar reconstruction (CPR) and volume rendering images. The arterial phase volume was evaluated with maximum intensity projection (MIP), 3D volume rendering, CPR and MPR for precise evaluation of the mesenteric vessels and bowel. Sagittal images helped in assessing the origin of the mesenteric arteries from the aorta and its variations.

Coronal images and performing CT angiography using maximum intensity projection (MIP) and volume rendering were valuable for assessing vascular anatomy and sites of interruption of the arterial blood supply by emboli [6-8]. Multidetector Computed Tomography (CT) scans images suggested bowel wall thickening (wall thickness > 3 mm in non-collapsed small bowel) or thinning (paper thin), Attenuation of mucosa in pre-contrast images, variable or non-mucosal enhancement on post contrast CT images, variable degree of bowel distension, pneumatosis intestinalis, stranding of mesenteric fat, ascites, atherosclerotic calcification/ plaque, thrombosis of porto-mesenteric veins and superior mesenteric or portal venous gas.

Results

We did MDCT and CTA examinations

within 1-2 hours after getting the patient requisition in most of the cases and no minor or major complications were observed. Data were presented as percentage and mean. 30 patients (23 males and 7 females, sex ratio 3.3:1) out of clinicopathologically highly suspected 140 patients constituted the final study group with abnormal CT angiographic (CTA) diagnostic of acute mesenteric ischemia.

Their age ranged between 50 and 76 years. (mean 60.5 years) The most prevalent MDCT findings in 30 patients with acute mesenteric ischemia were absence of wall enhancement on CECT in 22 patients (75%), bowel wall thickening in 21 (70%) and bowel distension in 21 patients (70%) (Table 1). We observed arterial occlusion in 22(73.3) patients, venous occlusion in 2 (6.7%) and non-occlusive mesenteric ischaemia in 6(20%) patients. Arterial embolism was seen in 14 (46.6%) patients and arterial thrombosis in 8 (26.7%) patients (Table 2)

Final diagnosis

Acute mesenteric ischemia was surgically proven in 22 patients out of 30 patients with arterial occlusion (both embolism and thrombosis), however 6 patients with NOMI and 2 patients with SMV thrombosis were treated conservatively.

NOMI responded to medical management and the diagnosis of AMI was done on the basis of clinicopathological follow up. The venous thrombosis responded to anticoagulant therapy which showed improved bowel appearance on interval follow up CT scans. Both MDCT and CTA gave an accurate diagnosis of the underlying cause of acute mesenteric ischemia in 30 patients, which constituted the final study group approved by the final diagnosis based on surgical exploration, laboratory parameters and interval clinico-imaging follow up with 100% sensitivity and 90% specificity.

Table 1: MDCT findings in patients with acute mesenteric ischaemia (n=30)

MDCT findings	Number of cases (out of 30),n (%)
Thickened bowel wall	21(70)
Paper thin bowel	9 (30)
Bowel distension	21(70)
High attenuation wall on NCCT	5 (16.7)
Non enhanced bowel wall on CECT	22 (75)
Pneumatosis intestinalis	3 (10)
Stranding of mesenteric fat	20 (66.7)
Ascites	12 (40)

MDCT; multidetector CT; AMI; acutemesenteric ischemia; NCCT, noncontrast CT; CECT: Contrast enhanced CT

Table 2: Computed tomography angiography (CTA) suggesting the cause of AMI (n=30).

CTA findings	Number of cases (out of 30),n (%)
Arterial Occlusion	22 (73.3)
MAE	14 (46.6)
MAT	8 (26.7)
Venous Occlusion MVT	2 (6.7)
NOMI	6 (20)

MAE; mesenteric arterial embolism, MAT; mesenteric arterial thrombosis, MVT; mesenteric venous thrombosis, NOMI; nonocclusive mesenteric

Figure 1a: Superior mesenteric artery (SMA) embolism in 55 year old male with sudden onset severe abdominal pain shown. Axial CECT image of the upper abdomen showing a hypodense filling defect suggestive of an embolus (arrow) in proximal SMA

Figure 1b: Superior mesenteric artery (SMA) embolism in 55 year old male with sudden onset severe abdominal pain shown. CT Angiography in sagittal view suggestive of an embolus (arrow) in proximal Superior Mesentric Artery (SMA)

Figure 2a : Superior mesenteric artery (SMA) thrombosis in 64 year old male with disproportionate persistent pain abdomen. Axial CECT image of the upper abdomen revealing filling defect suggestive of thrombus (arrow) in mid/distal SMA.

Figure 2b: Superior mesenteric artery (SMA) thrombosis in 64 year old male with disproportionate persistent pain abdomen CT Angiography suggestive of long segment thrombus (arrow) in mid/distal SMA, causing its mild expansion.

Figure 3: Acute mesenteric arterial embolism with non-enhancing bowel wall in 58 year old female. Axial CECT image of lower abdomen showing paper thin bowel wall with lack of contrast enhancement (horizontal arrow) .Adjacent mesenteric fat stranding also seen (vertical arrow).

Figure 4: Acute mesenteric arterial embolism with transmural bowel infarction in 68 year old female. Axial CECT images show gas (arrow) in the bowel wall (pneumatosis intestinalis).

Discussion

In our study, a total of 30 patients showed positive CTA and MDCT findings explaining the underlying cause of mesenteric vascular ischemia, our findings were similar with Ofer *et al* [9] who performed 93 consecutive studies on a group of 91 patients with clinically suspected acute mesenteric ischemia, used abdominal CT angiography as the first diagnostic procedure and it was found to be diagnostic in 92 studies. The most frequent MDCT findings with abnormal CT angiographic findings were non enhancing bowel on contrast enhanced CT in 22(75%) patients, bowel wall thickening in 21 (70%) patients and bowel distension in 21(70%) patients, these findings were more or less similar to Al- Azzazy *et al* [10] in whose study bowel wall thickening, bowel distension and non-enhanced bowel wall on post- contrast CT were the most prevalent MDCT findings in patients with clinical suspicion of mesenteric ischemia. At the same time, study done by Serpa *et al* [11] suggested that as these bowel wall changes (bowel wall thickening, bowel distension and bowel enhancement

pattern) were encountered in a wide variety of other pathologies too, so, they lack specificity.

The underlying pathology of AMI was accurately detected on CTA in our study, where SMA occlusion with arterial thrombo-embolism was the commonest cause in 22 (73.3%) patients, non-occlusive type the second commonest cause with 6 (20%) patients, whereas SMV occlusion observed in 2 patients (6.7%). Our results showed similarity with Ofer *et al* [9] study who found occlusive mesenteric ischaemia in 14 out of total 18 patients (~77.8%) and non-occlusive cause in 4 (~22.2%) patients. Our results were also close to Al- Azzazy *et al.* [10] study in which abnormal CTA findings were observed in 21 out of 57 (~37%). We were able to correctly diagnose mesenteric ischemia in total 30 patients using both MDCT and CTA and explained the clinical presentation and disproportionate abdominal pain in them with 100% sensitivity and 90% specificity, these findings showed consistency with Barmase *et al* [12] study in which MDCT was able

to diagnose mesenteric ischemia in all 16 patients with 100% sensitivity and specificity and 9 patients out of 16 underwent surgical exploration. In our study 22 out of 30 were explored surgically. Our study gave sensitivity (100%) and specificity (90%) close to the study conducted by. Al- Azzazy *et al* [10] also, where MDCT and CTA gave an accurate diagnosis of the cause of mesenteric ischemia with 100% sensitivity and specificity.

We observed pneumatosis intestinalis in only 3(10%) patients out of 30 patients with AMI, in which laparotomy revealed irreversible ischaemia and bowel infarction, so, this MDCT finding was found to be a specific finding suggesting bowel ischemia in late stages and it was also consistent with multiple previously published studies [6-8]. In present study, MDCT explained the cause of mesenteric ischemia in 30 out of 140 patients (21.4%) as well as helped to make other definitive alternative diagnosis of severe abdominal pain in 87 patients out of 140 patients (62%). Our results were more or less close to Ofer *et al* [9] study, where MDCT and CT angiography were able to make an alternative diagnosis in 38 patients (51%). Our findings also agreed with Kirkpatrick *et al* [8] in whose study CT helped in making a definitive alternative diagnosis in 21 patients (58%).

The most significant limitations in our work was relatively less number of patients in final study group, as acute mesenteric ischemia is a rare pathology. Surgery was not performed in a total of 8 patients, in whom specific clinical findings and interval clinico-patho-radiological follow up helped to make a definitive diagnosis.

Conclusion

In suspected cases of mesenteric ischemia, MDCT and CTA are non- invasive, fast and accurate imaging modality able to evaluate mesenteric vascular structures as

well as the bowel wall changes and adjacent mesentery, thus accurately

detecting the primary cause of mesenteric ischemia, which results in early and timely diagnosis and prompt management. They are also helpful in confirmation or exclusion of various other differentials of acute abdominal conditions. Management includes restoration of mesenteric blood flow surgically with resection of the non-viable bowel. Endovascular management is an effective treatment option in early-stage cases with reversible mesenteric ischemia [13,14].

References

1. Klar E, Rahmanian PB, Bücken A, Hauenstein K, Jauch KW, Luther B. Acute mesenteric ischemia: a vascular emergency. *Dtsch Arztebl Int* 2012; 109(14):249–256
2. Acosta S, mesenteric ischemia. *Curr opin Crit Care*.2015;21:171-8
3. Clair DG, Beach JM. Mesenteric ischemia. *N Engl JMed*.2016;374:959-68
4. Adaba F, Askari A, Dastur J, *et al*. Mortality after acute primary mesenteric infarction: a systematic review and meta-analysis of observational studies. *Colorectal Dis* 2015;17(7):566–577
5. Beaulieu RJ, Arnaoutakis KD, Abularrage CJ, Efron DT, Schneider E, Black JH. Comparison of open and endovascular treatment of acute mesenteric ischemia. *J Vasc Surg*. 2014; 59:159-64
6. 4.Furukawa A. Kanasaki S, Kono N, *et al*. CT diagnosis of acute mesenteric ischaemia from various causes. *AJR* 2009; 192:408-16
7. Horton KM, Fishman EK. Multidetector CT angiography in the diagnosis of mesenteric ischemia. *Radiol Clin North Am* 2007;45(2):275–288.
8. Kirkpatrick IDC, Kroeker MA, Greenberg HM. Biphase CT with mesenteric CT angiography in the evaluation of acute mesenteric

- ischaemia: initial experience. *Radiology* 2003;229:91-8
9. Ofer A, Abadi S, Nitecki S, Karran J, *et al.* Multidetector Ct angiography in the evaluation of acute mesenteric ischaemia. *Eur Radiol* 2009;19:24-30
 10. Al-azzazy MZ, Hasan DI, El-Sherbeni ME, Gameel AM. Multidetector CT and CT angiography in mesenteric ischaemia. *Egypt J Radiol Nucl Med* 2012;43:337-45
 11. Serpa BS, Tachibana A, Baroni RH, *et al.* Acute and chronic mesenteric ischaemia: MDCT findings. *J Vasc Bras* 2010;9(3):156-63
 12. Barmase M, Kang M, Wig J, *et al.* Role of multidetector CT angiography in the evaluation of suspected mesenteric ischaemia. *Eur J Radiol* 2011;80(3):e582-7
 13. Kärkkäinen JM, Lehtimäki TT, Saari P, *et al.* Endovascular therapy as a primary revascularization modality in acute mesenteric ischemia. *Cardiovasc Intervent Radiol* 2015;38(5):1119–1129.
 14. Beaulieu RJ, Arnaoutakis KD, Abularrage CJ, Efron DT, Schneider E, Black JH III. Comparison of open and endovascular treatment of acute mesenteric ischemia. *J Vasc Surg* 2014;59(1):159–164.